

Goal-Oriented Semantic Modules for SAR Ship Detection

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Abstract—Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) imaging is a vital technology for maritime surveillance, enabling ship detection under all weather conditions and lighting scenarios. Recent advancements in Deep Learning (DL) have substantially improved the performance of SAR Ship Detection systems. Among these advancements, various adaptations of the You Only Look Once (YOLO) model have been developed to address the unique challenges of SAR imaging, such as varying ship sizes, complex backgrounds, and high noise levels. This paper reviews and analyzes studies incorporating innovative techniques like Multi-Scale Feature Extraction (MSFE), Attention Mechanisms, and Lightweight Neural Networks (LNN) to enhance detection accuracy and efficiency. Through a comparative analysis, we evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of these adaptations across different datasets. Additionally, we present the implementation of a modified YOLOv5 Small (YOLOv5s) model on the Pixel-wise Segmentation SAR Ship Detection Dataset (PSeg-SSDD), achieving a balance between accuracy and computational efficiency. Our findings demonstrate the model’s suitability for advanced maritime monitoring applications.

Index Terms—Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), Deep Learning (DL), SAR Ship Detection, You Only Look Once (YOLO), Multi-Scale Feature Extraction (MSFE), Attention Mechanisms, Lightweight Neural Networks (LNN), Pixel-wise Segmentation SAR Ship Detection Dataset (PSeg-SSDD).

I. INTRODUCTION

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) technology is a powerful tool for earth observation, capable of producing high-resolution images regardless of weather conditions or time of day. Unlike optical sensors, SAR systems emit microwave signals and capture their reflections, enabling effective operation under cloud cover or in total darkness. This capability makes SAR invaluable for continuous maritime surveillance, facilitating ship detection across vast oceanic expanses [1]. Ship detection is crucial for monitoring maritime traffic, enforcing laws against illegal fishing, securing borders, and protecting

the environment. Effective detection supports timely responses to maritime accidents, search and rescue operations, and law enforcement activities in international waters [2]. Traditional methods like patrol ships and optical satellite imaging are limited by visibility conditions and high resource demands [3].

The YOLO (You Only Look Once) model revolutionizes computer vision with its fast and accurate object detection capabilities, framing detection as a single regression problem for real-time identification [4]. Applying YOLO to SAR images for ship detection presents challenges such as high noise levels, complex backgrounds, and variable target sizes. SAR’s sensitivity to surface roughness and moisture results in high false alarm rates [5], requiring significant adaptations to enhance noise suppression and sensitivity to varying object sizes [6].

Adapting YOLO models to SAR imaging has made significant progress with modifications that enhance precision and efficiency. Key advancements include the Low-Frequency Encoder Network (LFer-Net), which uses space-to-depth convolution (SPDConv) and inception depthwise convolution (InceptionDWConv) to tackle low-resolution and multi-scale challenges [7]. The Multi-Scale Feature Attention YOLO (MSFA-YOLO) employs a fused attention mechanism and Densely Connected Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling (DenseASPP) for detailed semantic capture and small target identification in cluttered backgrounds [8]. Both models show substantial reductions in false positives and improvements in detection accuracy on datasets like the Segmentation SAR Ship Detection Dataset (SSDD) and High-Resolution SAR Image Dataset (HRSID).

YOLO-Lite is a lightweight model for real-time processing on edge devices, achieving high performance through strategic re-engineering of convolutional layers and attention mechanisms [9]. Comparative analysis highlights the strengths of each adaptation: MSFA-YOLO excels in complex conditions, while LFer-Net offers robust feature extraction with

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minimal computational overhead, suitable for limited processing scenarios. Transformer-based YOLO adaptations, though resource-intensive, significantly improve contextual analysis in dense maritime traffic areas [10] [11]. The trend is toward architectures that manage SAR complexities without increasing computational demands [12]. For example, ECFP-Net enhances detection with speckle noise suppression (FMK), Edge Constraint Structure (ECS), and the Semantic Feature Perception Module (SFPM) [9].

This paper focuses on developing and implementing an enhanced YOLOv5 Small (YOLOv5s) model specifically tailored for SAR ship detection on the Pixel-wise Segmentation SSDD (PSeg-SSDD). The goal is to achieve higher accuracy and reduced computational time by leveraging innovative methods that address the unique challenges posed by SAR imagery. By applying the enhanced YOLOv5s to the PSeg-SSDD, this study aims to demonstrate the model’s effectiveness in practical maritime monitoring applications [12] [8].

This paper is organized as follows: Section II details the methodology. Section III presents the experimental results. Finally, Section IV concludes with key findings and recommendations for further research.

II. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the advanced methodological changes applied to the YOLOv5s model to optimize its performance for SAR ship detection. The goal of this research is to improve the model’s accuracy and inference rate, which are crucial for real-time detection applications.

A. Dataset

This study utilizes the PSeg-SSDD [13], which consists of high-resolution SAR images showcasing a diverse range of marine vessels. In comparison to other datasets, SSDD offers a diverse range of ship sizes and complex backgrounds, making it particularly suitable for evaluating the performance of SAR ship detection models. The radar parameters for these images include a wavelength of 3.1 cm (X-band), a resolution of 1m x 1m, and a typical incidence angle range of 20 to 60 degrees. For our research, we focused on the PSeg-SSDD annotations, which mark each pixel of the image corresponding to a ship. This precise annotation is crucial for tasks requiring accurate localization, such as semantic segmentation. A total of 1160 annotated images were divided into three subsets: training (70%), validation (15%), and testing (15%). This division facilitates comprehensive learning and unbiased evaluation [14] [15].

B. Data Preprocessing

The preprocessing approach was specifically developed to enhance SAR images for the purpose of

improving detection using deep learning techniques. Each image underwent standard normalization to provide consistent lighting and contrast. Additionally, all images were resized to 640x640 pixels to match the required input resolution of YOLOv5s. To emphasize the significance of edge characteristics in SAR data and improve the model’s ability to differentiate ships from the complex background, we incorporated edge enhancement techniques into the preprocessing pipeline [16].

C. Model and Training

We incorporated architectural enhancements, building on the foundational YOLOv5s architecture. Standard convolutional layers were replaced by the EfficientConvModule, which includes depth-wise separable convolutions [17]:

$$y_{m,n,c} = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} x_{m+i,n+j,c} \cdot w_{i,j,c} \quad (1)$$

where x is the input feature map, w is the depth-wise convolution filter, y is the output feature map, m and n are spatial dimensions, c is the channel index, and k is the kernel size.

$$y_{m,n,c'} = \sum_{c=0}^{C-1} y_{m,n,c} \cdot w_{1,1,c,c'} \quad (2)$$

where C is the number of input channels and c' is the output channel index.

We also integrated Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) blocks for dynamic channel-wise feature recalibration [18]:

$$z_c = \frac{1}{H \times W} \sum_{i=1}^H \sum_{j=1}^W x_{i,j,c} \quad (3)$$

where H and W are the spatial dimensions of the input feature map, and c is the channel index.

$$s_c = \sigma(W_2 \cdot \text{ReLU}(W_1 \cdot z)) \quad (4)$$

where z is the squeezed feature map, W_1 and W_2 are weights of the fully connected layers, and σ denotes the sigmoid activation function.

These enhancements improve the model’s efficiency and focus on informative features for ship detection.

The model was trained on an NVIDIA Quadro GV100 GPU with 32 GB memory, leveraging the power of GPU acceleration. We initialized the model’s weights from a pre-trained state on the COCO dataset [19], utilizing the strengths of transfer learning. The model underwent fine-tuning for 99 epochs, with a batch size of 16. We used the SGD optimizer with an initial learning rate of 0.01, momentum of 0.95, and weight

Fig. 1: The Train Batch, Validation Batch Labels, and Validation Batch Prediction of PSeg-SSDD dataset using modified YOLOv5s.

decay of 0.001. The learning rate was dynamically adjusted based on the validation loss performance using a cosine annealing schedule. The loss was computed using Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) loss. Data augmentation strategies, including Hue, Saturation, Value (HSV) augmentations, were employed to prevent overfitting and ensure robustness against variations within the SAR imagery.

D. Optimization and Evaluation

During the inference phase, we fed the processed images into the optimized model to determine ship locations, assigning confidence scores to each detection. A custom implementation of Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) was applied to refine the prediction set. Extensive model optimization strategies, such as weight quantization and selective pruning, were implemented to enhance inference speed without compromising detection performance.

Performance evaluation was conducted using established metrics, including mean Average Precision (mAP) across varying Intersection over Union (IoU) thresholds, precision, and recall rates. These measures provide a comprehensive assessment of the model's predictive power and real-world applicability.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental results of the enhanced YOLOv5s model applied to the PSeg-SSDD dataset indicate exceptional performance in detecting and localizing maritime

vessels within SAR imagery. Fig. 1 illustrates a representative selection of detection results, where the model precisely identifies ships, marked by red bounding boxes and corresponding confidence scores.

A. Detection Performance

Throughout the dataset, the model maintained a consistent detection efficacy, demonstrating significant resilience to the characteristic noise of SAR images. Notably, the model's ability to detect ships in low-contrast situations, such as in image 000784.jpg, and to distinguish ships against dark backgrounds, as seen in image 000294.jpg, highlights its robustness. The detection precision is exemplified even with smaller and less conspicuous targets, which can often blend into the noisy background inherent in SAR data.

The model's precision was empirically evaluated, revealing a mAP of 96% at an IoU threshold of 0.5. This high mAP reflects the model's accuracy in aligning predicted bounding boxes with the actual locations of ships in the images.

Advanced features such as SE blocks and depth-wise separable convolutions have been integrated into the model, achieving approximately 108 frames per second (FPS). While this speed is slower than that of some other techniques, it remains sufficient for real-time SAR surveillance operations, underscoring the model's practical application in live maritime monitoring.

Our binary classifier effectively detects ships near coastal regions due to diverse training data, advanced preprocessing, and sophisticated model architecture.

Fig. 2: Results via different parameters and metrics

The dataset includes varied maritime environments, allowing the model to generalize well. Preprocessing techniques, such as edge enhancement, reduce background noise. Additionally, SE blocks and attention mechanisms help the model focus on ships and ignore coastal background features, ensuring high detection accuracy.

The corroborated results validate the proposed enhancements to the YOLOv5s architecture, establishing it as a highly accurate and efficient tool for ship detection in SAR imagery, suitable for real-world surveillance and maritime safety applications.

B. Training and Validation Metrics

Fig. 2 presents the training and validation loss metrics, as well as the precision, recall, and mAP over 99 epochs for the SAR ship detection modified model of the YOLOv5s algorithm. These metrics are useful for understanding the model’s learning behavior and performance.

1) *Box Loss*: For Training Box Loss (Train/Box_Loss) and Validation Box Loss (Val/Box_Loss), which utilize IOU loss for bounding box regression, both training and validation box loss demonstrate a downward trend, indicating that the model is learning to accurately place bounding boxes around the target objects (ships) as training progresses. The training box loss shows a steep decrease initially, leveling out as it approaches a low value, suggesting that the model quickly learned the spatial features required for bounding box prediction. The validation loss decreases similarly, but with some fluctuation, which is normal in the validation phases as the model is tested against unseen data.

2) *Objectness Loss*: Regarding Training Object Loss (Train/Obj_Loss) and Validation Object Loss (Val/Obj_Loss), which are calculated using BCE loss, the objectness loss for both training and validation datasets initially trends downward. However, the Validation Object Loss (Val/Obj_Loss) decreases for approximately the first 10 epochs and then shows an increasing trend afterward. This loss measures how well the model

classifies objects vs. background, so a decrease in the initial phase indicates improving performance in distinguishing ships from noise in the SAR images.

The mAP at an IoU threshold of 0.5 fluctuates around high values, indicating the model’s good performance in overlapping its predictions with the ground truth. A high mAP value at this threshold is desirable and shows effective model learning. The overall mAP metric, which measures mAP averaged over IoU thresholds from 0.5 to 0.95 (in steps of 0.05), is a stringent measure of performance. The graph shows more variation compared to mAP at a threshold of 0.5, which is expected as higher IoU thresholds are more difficult to achieve. The values here are lower, reflecting the increased difficulty of meeting these stricter criteria, but they appear to trend around a reasonably stable value after the initial learning period, suggesting the model’s reasonable performance across a range of IoU thresholds.

C. Comparative Analysis

To assess the performance of our modified YOLOv5s model, we conducted a series of experiments comparing it with other state-of-the-art models. Table I presents a comparative analysis of detection accuracy and computational efficiency. Our modified YOLOv5s achieved a mAP of 96% at an IoU threshold of 0.5, surpassing the performance of other models like MSFA-YOLO and LFER-Net. The recall and precision rates were 93% and 92%, respectively, indicating a high rate of correctly identified detections with minimal false positives. Additionally, the model demonstrated an inference speed of approximately 108 FPS, suitable for real-time SAR surveillance operations.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study explored various adaptations of the YOLO model tailored to the challenges of SAR ship detection. Key enhancements, including advanced convolution techniques and attention mechanisms, have enabled these models to effectively handle high noise levels and complex backgrounds in SAR images. Notable improvements in detection accuracy and computational

TABLE I: Comparative Analysis of SAR Ship Detection Techniques

Model Name	Key Innovations	Accuracy	Computational Efficiency	Adaptability	Applications	References
LFer-Net	SPDConv, InceptionDWConv	High	Moderate	Good for dense ships	Maritime traffic monitoring	[7]
MSFA-YOLO	DenseASPP, fused attention	Very High	High	Excellent	Comprehensive surveillance	[8]
YOLO-Lite	Pruning techniques, optimized convolutions	Moderate	Very High	Moderate	Real-time on edge devices	[9]
ECFP-Net	FMK, ECS, SFPM	Very High	High	Excellent	SAR image target detection, maritime surveillance	[12]
Transformer-YOLO	Transformer-based contextual analysis	Very High	Moderate to High	Excellent for dense traffic	Complex maritime environments	[10]
Our Model	EfficientConvModule, SE blocks	Very High	High	Excellent	Advanced maritime monitoring	This Work

efficiency were demonstrated by models such as LFer-Net and MSFA-YOLO, highlighting their capabilities in diverse and cluttered environments.

Our modified YOLOv5s model, implemented on the PSeg-SSDD, achieves a balance between accuracy and computational efficiency, making it well-suited for advanced maritime monitoring. The main contributions of our approach include a significant reduction in false positives, enhanced detection accuracy across various ship sizes and complex backgrounds, and improved computational efficiency for real-time applications.

Future research directions include further improvements in algorithmic efficiency and accuracy, potentially incorporating cutting-edge techniques like deep reinforcement learning. Extending these advanced detection models to other remote sensing applications could provide significant benefits in areas such as environmental monitoring and urban development. The advancements in YOLO adaptations for SAR ship detection underscore the importance of ongoing research in this field for enhancing maritime security and monitoring capabilities.

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